

Nature Materials

Enhanced Functional Composites

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August 6, 2025
ICCM24

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Cork Employed as an Environmentally Friendly Solution for Sandwich Composite Structures

I Sandwich Composites

Sandwich Composites

- ◆ Core and top & bottom face sheets
- ◆ High stiffness-to-weight ratios
- ◆ Used often in aerospace/transport industries

Popular Core Materials

Honeycombs of
Nomax[®] or Kevlar[®]

Rohacell[®] Foams

High stiffness-to-weight ratios cause poor damping/acoustic performances

I Sandwich Acoustic and Damping

- High strength-to-weight and stiffness-to-weight ratios cause high noise radiation
- Poor damping and acoustic performance
- Effects on comfort and material lifespan
- Previous work on geometry and core material
 - Shear modulus effect (Sargianis, J. and Suhr J. Composite Science & Technology (2012, 2012))
- Audible frequency range: 16Hz~20,000Hz (20kHz)

http://www.qinetiq.com/home/newsroom/news_releases_homepage/2004/4th_quarter/QinetiQ_provides_key_technology_expertise_for_Boeing_7E7_Dreamliner.html

<http://www.mrc-cbu.cam.ac.uk/history/electronicarchive/heatstress.html>

Core Material Properties

	Rohacell 110 WF	Rohacell 110 IG	Kevlar Honeycomb	Nomex Honeycomb	Cork Agglomerate
Shear Modulus (MPa)	70	50	147	30	2.4
Density (kg/m ³)	110	110	108	29	130
G/ρ	0.636	0.455	1.370	1.038	0.02

Prior to compression Under compression After unloading

Bending Stiffness Measurement

- In order for the cork agglomerate core beam to be a viable replacement, it should have a similar bending stiffness:

Carbon Fiber Face Sheets with cork (Top) and Rohacell 110IG (Bottom) cores

I Test Set-up for Noise & Vibration Characterization

- Setup on a vibration isolation table to reduce external vibrations
- Clamped-Clamped
- Random vibration from 20-10000 Hz
- Two microaccelerometers at 64 equidistant points along the beam to get FRF
- Fourier Transform to convert domains

I Wave Number Method

- The FRFs (Frequency Response Function) are transformed into the Wave Number domain using a Fourier Transform.

- From this data we can determine the *coincidence frequency*, since:

$$\text{Wave Number } (k) = \frac{\text{Vibrational Frequency } (\omega)}{\text{Vibrational Wave Speed } (c)}$$

Dispersion Plot

- How can we determine the coincidence frequency?
 - Dispersion Plot:

Dispersion plot and Wave number amplitude

I Damping Characterization

- Sandwich structures' vibrational damping performance is characterized by 3 db method.
- Experiments measured damping via ASTM E756-05:
3 decibel/half power bandwidth method:

$$\eta = \frac{f_2 - f_1}{f_0}$$

Damping Factor (Structural Loss Factor)

Natural Cork's Remarkable Properties

Current Applications

Wine stopper

Transportation

Insulating materials

Daily supplies
(boards, coasters, etc.)

Cork Agglomerate vs Expanded Cork

- Both are agglomerate sheets from cork granules
- Different processing techniques
- Generally recycled
- Natural and renewable
- Advantages and Disadvantages
- Cork has a cellular structure
 - Different principal directions and cell shapes

www.ulsinc.de

www.soundviewwindowanddoor.com/

Mano. Creep Recovery Behaviour of Cork

I Amorime Visit in 2012 (Expanded Cork)

Cork Harvesting (Portugal)

I Amorime Visit in 2012 (Expanded Cork)

I Amorime Visit in 2012 (Expanded Cork)

Expanded Cork Core Sandwich Composites

Dispersion Plot (Acoustic)

Loss Factor Plot (Structural Damping)

Rohacell 110 IG Foam

Expanded Cork

Cork core sandwich composites showed improved acoustics, vibrational damping performances

I Expanded Cork Core Sandwich Composites

❖ Damping Characterization

- FRF at resonant frequencies
- 3 dB method to find structural loss factor
- Higher loss factor correlates to increased damping
- Cork shows high improvements in damping
- Drops off around 4000 Hz

$$\eta = \frac{\Delta\omega}{\omega_n}$$

❖ Bending Characterization

Core Material	Density, ρ (kg/m ³)	Bending Stiffness, D (10 ⁶ N*mm ²)	Core Shear Modulus, G (MPa)
Expanded Cork Agglomerate	120	24.6	2.4
Rohacell® 110 IG	110	24.9	50
Rohacell® 110 WF	110	27.9	70

Expanded Cork Core Sandwich Composites

Low-Velocity Impact Testing

Impact energy: 10J

Biodegradable Suberin/PLA Blends

Cork Wastes: Recycle & Upcycle

De-polymerization
(Selective Extraction)

< Biodegradable Materials >

< Artificial Cork Foams >

< Functional Composites >

Potential Applications

Sandwich Composites

Biodegradable plastics

Automotive Parts

Seals & Gaskets

Engine Mounts & Bushes

Flame Retardant Materials (for EVs)

Interior Parts

Biodegradable Suberin/PLA Blends

International Standards for Biodegradable Plastics

90% biodegradation in 6 months

60% biodegradation in 6 months

90% biodegradation in 6 months

60% biodegradation in 6 months

Biodegradable PLA Disposable Cup

Brittleness Challenge in PLA

Plasticizer

- Petroleum-based Plasticizer
→ Environmental Pollution
- Biodegradable plasticizer (PHA, PBAT)
→ High Cost

Suberin Extraction from Potato Skin

Plant Physiol. Vol. 149, 2009

- Long alkyl chain with Ester groups
→ Biodegradable material
- Suberin as Plasticizer
→ Addressing PLA Brittleness
- Suberin extraction from Potato skin waste
→ Eco-Friendly & Cost Down

Conformal Cooling Channel Mold

Conformal Cooling Channel
via CFD and Additive Manufacturing

1D Cooling
channel

3D Cooling
channel

- Excellent Heat Transfer Performance
→ Reducing Cooling Cycle Time
- Uniform Temperature Distribution
→ Reducing Manufacturing Defect Rate

“At least 30% Productivity Improvement is expected”,

According to Global Technology Research
at Samsung Electronics DX Division

Suberin Extraction from Waste Natural Resources

Materials

PLA
(Poly lactic acid)

Product Name	Density	MFI (190°C/2.16kg)	Tensile Strength	Young's Modulus	Elongation at Break
LUMINY®	1.24 g/cm ³	3g/10min	45 MPa	3500 MPa	3~4%

Suberin

Cork

Potato Skin

Extraction

Blending

Filtration

Ethanol Evaporation

Coagulation

Freeze drying

Condensation polymerization

Alkaline Hydrolysis of Cork and Potato skin Suberin

Alkaline Hydrolysis (Saponification)

Coagulation

Polycondensation of Cork and Potato skin Suberin

Suberin/PLA Blends

Cork
Suberin

Potato
Suberin

Suberin

PLA

Extruding

at 170 → 190 → 200 → 200 → 190°C

Suberin/PLA Masterbatch

Hot press
@ 190°C for 5min

1 wt% CSe/PLA

1 wt%
PSe/PLA

Injection molding
@ 200°C

3 wt%
PSe/PLA

Thermal Analysis

Ramp rate: 10°C/min, Atmosphere: Nitrogen, 2nd heating curve

	T_g (°C)	T_{cc} (°C)	T_{m1} (°C)	T_{m2} (°C)	ΔH_m (J/g)	aX_c (%)	$T_{on\ set}$ (°C)	$T_{5\%}$ (°C)
neat PLA	58.4	107.0	150.9	156.1	43.1	46.04	282.09	270.46
1 wt% CSe/PLA	57.3	118.0	152.5	-	30.3	32.69	295.02	276.27
3 wt% CSe/PLA	53.5	110.3	148.8	155.3	31.1	34.25	291.12	275.9
5 wt% CSe/PLA	52.3	116.4	147.4	153.5	31.3	35.20	276.82	264.65
1 wt% PSe/PLA	54.7	122.1	153.2	-	33.8	36.47	289.77	282.71
3 wt% PSe/PLA	50.9	117.5	147.3	153.3	32.2	35.46	284.84	267.22
5 wt% PSe/PLA	48.6	116.4	144.6	151.5	31.9	35.87	281.78	271.1

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

Distance between polymer chains ↑

Free volume ↑

Molecular chains can move at lower temperature

Mechanical Properties

Standard : ASTM D882-18
 Load Cell : 250N
 Ramp rate : 5mm/min
 Film specimen size : 100*5*0.5mm
 Gauge length : 50mm

Biodegradation Test

Standard : ISO 20200 : 2015, Temperature : 58 ± 2°C, Institute : FITI

sample \ week	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
neat PLA															
CSe/PLA															
PSe/PLA															

Biodegradation: over 90% in 12 wks

$$D = \frac{m_i - m_r}{m_i} \times 100$$

m_i Initial dry mass of the test material

m_r The dry mass of the residual test material recovered by sieving

CFD Analysis of Conformal Cooling Channel

Baffle-type Cooling Channel Conformal Cooling Channel: Spiral Type

Thermal Properties

Steel Material Properties	Value
Thermal Conductivity	40 W/m/K
Specific Heat	0.7878 J/g·°C
Density	7.8 g/cm ³

Thermal Analysis

CFD Results & Analysis

Type	T _{max} (°C)	T _{min} (°C)	ΔT (°C)
Baffle	68	49	19
Conformal	54 (21% ↓)	43	11 (42% ↓)

Temp. Distribution of Baffle/Conformal Cooling Channels

Process Optimization of L-PBF

Metal Additive Manufacturing & Optimization process

Densification based Quality Assessment

Conformal Cooling Channel Manufacturing

Fabrication of Conformal Cooling Channel

Surface Postprocessing

Injection Molding Process using Conformal Cooling Channel

Suberin/PLA Master-batch

Injection Molding w/ Conformal Cooling Channel

Injection Molding Process

CSe/PLA

PSe/PLA

Start-up
EcoPoly

Biodegradable Suberin/PLA Cups

Conclusions & Acknowledgement

■ **Cork Agglomerations**

- 1) Environmentally friendly solution for sandwich composites
- 2) Outstanding NVH improvement w/o compromise in bending stiffness and lightweight

■ **Suberin from Potato Skin, which is natural resource waste**

- 1) Biodegradable plasticizer for PLA, reducing brittleness
- 2) Excellent biodegradability with strong potential for commercial plastics

This work envisions cork-based materials contributing to energy absorbing structures and biodegradable plastics in the near future.

■ **Acknowledgement**

I would like to thank Boeing Company, and the Ministry of Science and ICT (South Korea) for their financial support for these research works!

Thank you for your attention!

Composite Materials & Structures Lab
<http://composite-moduli.org/>